

The breeding line did not suffer any visible damage during the 1987 outbreak when typical hopperburn appeared on susceptible japonica variety Reihou.

Honeydew measurements with pH indicator paper and parafilm sachet methods revealed that 1990 and 1991 BPH immigrants fed equally as much on Saikai 184 as on susceptible Reihou. They have

improved their ability to feed on indica variety IR26 (with *Bph 1* gene), but not on IR42 (*bph 2* gene) (see figure).

Breeding experiments with potted plants similarly showed that recent BPH immigrants reproduced as prolifically on Saikai 184 as on Reihou and other breeding lines (such as Saikai 190 and Nankai 111) with the *Bph 1* gene.

Reproductive performance on IR26 was not yet equivalent to that on Reihou. BPH produced few (if any) progeny on IR42.

Findings indicate that BPH immigrants in Japan are significantly changing from biotype 1 to biotype 2. This change may correspond to a possible biotype shift occurring recently in northern Vietnam and southern China BPH populations. □

Effect of rice stage and tungro (RTD) intensity on the infectivity of green leafhopper (GLH) in fields

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The epidemiological role of RTD-infected ricefields as the virus source depends on whether an infective vector population is produced. GLH is an abundant and efficient RTD transmitter. We studied the infectivity of GLH adults collected in rice and ratoon fields at

different RTD intensity levels by using the transmission test.

We collected insects by sweeping mainly in 1987-90 wet seasons at 79 selected sites planted to GLH-susceptible cultivars. RTD intensity at the sweeping site was estimated by a starch-iodine test of 100 sample leaves.

Sixty insects per site were individually allowed 1-d inoculation access to Cisadane seedlings in test tubes. The seedlings were transplanted in screen cages and treated with insecticide to prevent contamination from hatchings. Diagnosis was based on visual symptoms and confirmed by starch-iodine test made 3 wk after inoculation.

The percentage of positive RTD transmitters increased with the percentage of infected hills in all three rice stage categories (see figure). The relation appeared to be curvilinear 5-7

Effect of rice stage and disease intensity on the percentage of infective *Nephotettix virescens* adults in fields.^a Indonesia, 1987-90.

Rice stage	Hills infected in fields	
	<60%	>60%
5-7 WT	10.20 a	34.21 a
8-10 WT	8.45 a	27.28 b
Ratoon	13.23 a	26.81 b

^aIn a column, means (arc sin transformed) followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P = 0.05 by DMRT.

and 8-10 wk after transplanting (WT). The rank correlation coefficient was significant at the 0.1% level ($r_s = 0.897$ for 5-7 WT, 0.923 for 8-10 WT, and 0.914 for ratoon). Infectivity of GLH in severely infected fields (>60% hills infected) was highest 5-7 WT (see table).

Results suggest that ricefields severely infected during early growing stages are virus sources in asynchronous rice planting areas. □

Relation of the infectivity of *N. virescens* adults to the incidence of RTD in rice and ratoon fields. Indonesia, 1987-90

Wind tunnel for measuring rice plant attraction to insect predators and parasitoids

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Increasing evidence exists that plant odor, color, shape, texture, or infrared radiation may help guide parasitoids and predators to successfully locate their host or prey, colonize, and use crop habitat. A potentially fruitful approach for managing rice pests is to select varieties that resist pests and simultaneously provide a favorable habitat for the pests' natural enemies.

We devised the wind tunnel as a way to measure the attraction of natural

enemies to different rice genotypes (Fig. 1, 2). The tunnel has four main parts: air source, mixing chamber, air conduction box, and flight chamber. The air source is a 120-V ventilating fan with variable voltage regulator that controls speed. A galvanized iron tube connected to the mixing chamber houses the fan. Charcoal and cheesecloth filter the air entering the chamber.

The mixing chamber, made of galvanized iron sheeting, conveys air from the fan to the conduction box. An aluminum screen and two filters (nylon mesh and charcoal) help to reduce turbulence and clean the air.

The flight chamber is a plexiglass box with two open ends. The end opposite the fan has a detachable nylon mesh cover.

1. Side view of wind tunnel with the plexiglass tube inside the flight chamber.

2. Rear view of the wind tunnel.

Potted rice plants are placed in the flight chamber in two floor openings. Plants are separated by a plexiglass divider. Sliding windows on each side of the chamber allow entry to the plants and insect release.

Two 40-W cool-white fluorescent lamps are in the middle of the flight chamber. The chamber floor has alternating black and white stripes to help disrupt insect visual orientation.

To bioassay smaller parasitoids, we open the downwind end of the flight chamber and place a plexiglass tube with adjustable height inside to restrict the flight arena. This makes tracking of small insects easier. Both ends of the tube are covered with nylon mesh. Light and other stimuli can be excluded by covering the wind tunnel with a dark cloth tent that is still large enough to admit observers. □